

orange leaves 25 d later. The plants were slightly stunted and had more tillers than the control plants. BPH-inoculated *Oryza nivara* developed similar symptoms but those exposed to GLH did not.

Dried leaves of infected TN1 plants were sent to IRRI for serological tests. In a latex test using antiserum to rice grassy stunt virus (GSV), sap of the dried leaves reacted positively up to 1:8 dilution; sap of GSV-infected fresh leaves collected at IRRI reacted positively at 1:512 dilution; and sap of virus-free fresh leaves did not react, even at 1:1 dilution (Table 2).

We therefore identified the new disease as a strain of GSV. It is similar to GSV strain 2 in the Philippines. So far there are no reports from India of BPH-transmitted leaf yellowing. □

Table 1. Transmission of the new virus to TN1 and *O. nivara* by *N. virescens* and *N. lugens*. Coimbatore, India, and IRRI.

Insect	TN1		<i>O. nivara</i>	
	Inoculated	Infected	Inoculated	Infected
<i>N. virescens</i>	25	0	6	0
<i>N. lugens</i>	61	19	18	9

Table 2. Serological reaction of the sap of leaves infected with new virus or GSV to GSV antiserum by latex test, IRRI.

Sample	Reaction to given sap dilution									
	Undiluted	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512
Dried TN1 leaf infected with new virus	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
Fresh TN1 leaf infected with GSV	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Fresh TN1 leaf free from virus	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

+ = positive, - = negative.

Rice yield loss to sheath blight (ShB)

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ShB, caused by *Thanatephorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk, normally infects rice at tillering stage. ShB damage is increasing in Thailand.

In Jul-Dec 1983, we studied yield loss caused by different stages of ShB infestation to determine an economic threshold at which to apply chemical controls. The experiment was in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications of 5 treatments of different disease intensities: 0, 3, 5, 7, and 9 by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice. RD7, the most ShB-susceptible variety, was transplanted in 6- × 4-m plots and artificially

inoculated at tillering by inserting a packet of mycelia and sclerotia of *T. cucumeris* in each hill. Validamycin was used to keep disease intensity at the

Relationship between lesion length and percentages of yield loss, straw weight loss, and empty grains. Bangkhen, Thailand.

desired levels. Straw weight, grain weight, and number of empty grains were analyzed.

Infected plants with disease severity 3, 5, 7, and 9 reduced yield 15, 22, 28, and 40% (see table). Correlation between disease severity and percent yield loss, straw weight loss, and empty grains was a linear regression (see figure). □

Yield loss to bacterial blight (BB) in central Thailand

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BB, caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*, is a serious constraint in parts of Thailand.

We studied yield loss caused by BB at Bangkhen Rice Experiment Station in 1983 rainy season. RD1, a susceptible rice cultivar, was transplanted in 4 of 5 10-m² plots. Ammophos 16-20-0 was topdressed at 250 kg/ha, and plants were fully protected from other diseases and insect pests. Every hill in alternate rows was clip-inoculated at midtillering. When

Rice yield characters affected by different ShB severity, Bangkhen, Thailand.

Disease index	Av yield (kg/8 m)	Yield reduction (%)	Av straw wt (kg/8 m)	100-grain wt (g)	Empty grain (%)
0	4.05 a	0 a	26 a	3.0 a	21 a
3	3.42 b	15 b	24 ab	3.0 a	24 b
5	3.10 bc	22 bc	21 b	2.9 a	26 b
7	2.88 c	28 c	18 c	2.9 ab	30 c
9	2.39 d	40 d	15 c	2.6 b	33 d

Yield from rice with different intensities of BB at booting and milk stages, Bangkhen, Thailand.

Disease intensity ^a (%)	Grain wt (g)		Empty grain (%)	
	Booting stage	Milk stage	Booting stage	Milk stage
0	33.9	49.5	8	8
0-5	33.5	47.9	17	9
5-10	32.8	51.8	10	9
10-15	30.5	48.9	9	8
15-20	25.2	42.5	16	10
20-25	31.9	50.0	15	12
25-30	- ^b	51.3	- ^b	12

^a % disease severity in hill =

$$\frac{\text{sum of \% BB severity on flag leaves and 2d leaves}}{\text{number of tillers in hill} \times 2}$$

^b - = no information.

Estimated linear relationship between % empty grains and % BB intensity on rice variety RD1. Bangkhen, Thailand.

infection was uniform throughout the plots, 135 hills were randomly tagged in noninoculated rows.

Disease intensity was recorded at booting and milk stage. At booting stage, there was no correlation between grain weight, percentage of empty grains, and

disease severity. At milk stage, percentage of empty grains was significantly related to different disease intensities (see table). The correlation of empty grains and disease intensity was calculated as a simple linear regression equation $y = 8.2369 + 0.1306X^{**}$ (see figure), which

implied that increasing disease intensity increased percentage of empty grains.

Because yield component analysis was based on data from individual hills and because of the human influence, a high C. V. was noted. Therefore, grain weight did not correlate with disease intensity. □

Bacteriophage strain of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* from parts of Thailand

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The bacteriophage technique can be used to forecast a bacterial blight (BB) outbreak. Phage population, determined by plaque counting, shows the population density of the host bacterium *X. campestris* in irrigation water. Plaques or clear zones induced by the phage appear only on certain bacterial isolates. Therefore, it is necessary to select bacterial isolates that are susceptible to phage strains in areas where the bacteriophage technique will be used to predict BB outbreak.

We surveyed 19 provinces in central and northeastern Thailand for phage and host bacteria distribution (Table 1).

Forty *X. campestris* isolates were isolated from infected leaves using Wakimoto's potato semisynthetic agar (PSA) medium. Twenty-two bacteriophages were isolated from irrigation water by mixing 1 ml of the water sample with 2 ml of indicator bacterial suspension, then adding to 5 ml of the melted PSA medium. The mixture

was poured into sterilized petri dishes.

To maintain the phage, we transferred single plaques that developed 15-20 h later to test tubes containing a vitamin-free casein hydrolysate solution. Different lysotypes were determined by testing all bacteriophage samples against all bacterial isolates.

Table 1. Distribution of phage strains and *X. campestris* strains in some regions of Thailand.

Province	Region	<i>X. campestris</i> strain	Phage strain ^a
Lampang	Northern	B	-
Pichit	Northern	B	-
Petchaboon	Northern	E	-
Singhaburi	Central	B	-
Aungthong	Central	H	-
Chainat	Central	A, B, E	TBP ₁ , TBP ₄ , TBP ₅
Suphanburi	Central	B	TBP ₂
Bangkok	Central	A, B, C, D, E	TBP ₁ , TBP ₃ , TBP ₄
Pathumthani	Central	B	TBP ₁ , TBP ₄
Kanchanaburi	Central	A	-
Khon Khaen	Northeastern	A, C, F, G	TBP ₃
Maharakarm	Northeastern	B	TBP ₃
Kalasin	Northeastern	A, E	TBP ₃ , TBP ₅
Sakonnakorn	Northeastern	D, E	-
Udonthani	Northeastern	D, E	TBP ₅
Nongkai	Northeastern	D	TBP ₅
Nakornsajsim	Northeastern	A, C,	TBP ₃
Buriram	Northeastern	F	TBP ₃
Phatalung	Southern	E	-

^aA dash means not found.